

Geospatial driving factor analysis on the synergy between air pollution control and carbon mitigation in China

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Summary

Facing air pollution and carbon mitigation challenges, China actively pursues a “win-win” strategy for simultaneous reductions. This study evaluates synergistic governance performance between air pollution control and carbon mitigation in China under policy influence. It takes a GIS approach, based on spatial data analysis. Results show no significant improvement in synergistic governance performance under guidance of the major policies like "Clean Air Action" and "Blue Sky Defense". The relative activities during COVID-19 pandemic further hindered national effectiveness. Drivers exhibited spatial variations, while temporal heterogeneity remained relatively stable. These findings provide scientific insights that offer guidance for policymakers tackling environmental challenges.

KEYWORDS: Synergistic effect evaluation, Ordering degree, Coupling coordination degree, Driving factors, GWR (Geographically Weighted Regression)

1. Introduction

Since September 2020, following the proposal of a long-term mitigation goal for carbon neutrality by 2060 and carbon peak before 2030, China has attempted to seek for a unique pathway for deep carbon mitigation. Recognizing the interconnected nature of CO₂ and air pollutants' emissions, mainly generated from fossil fuel combustion and industrial production, China has adopted a regulatory strategy termed 'synergistic governance' (Wu et al., 2022). While numerous studies have explored the synergistic effects at sectoral and spatial scales, none have specifically investigated the performance of synergies between air pollution control and carbon mitigation during the 'COVID-19' pandemic. Thus, this study divides the time period into three intervals: the 'Clean Air Action' implementation period (2013-2017), the 'Blue Sky Defense' implementation period (2018-2019), and the period during the 'COVID-19' pandemic in 2020.

There are two objectives for this study:

- (1) To evaluate the synergistic governance performance at national scale.
- (2) To identify the spatial and temporal heterogeneity of the factors influencing the degree of synergistic governance.

2. Study area and data

Emissions data were sourced from the Multi-resolution Emission Inventory for China Dataset (MEIC), developed by Tsinghua University. This dataset integrates provincial-scale energy statistics (obtained from the China Energy Statistical Yearbook activity data) and the China Power Emissions Database (CPED) for the inventory compilation (Han et al., 2020). Given the spatial scope of the MEIC dataset, this study focuses on the 31 provinces in the mainland China, except Taiwan, Macau, and Hong Kong.

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Except from the emission data, the relative socio-economic and energy statistical data are collected from China Statistical Yearbook and Energy Statistical Yearbook from 2013 to 2020.

In this study, we treated the synergy between air pollution control (AP) and carbon mitigation (CM) as one system with the joint impact resulting from the intensity of interaction and the extent of harmonious development between AP and CM subsystems. The selected relative indicators were used to capture the dynamic nature and interactions within each subsystem. Key features, including total emission, emission intensity (emissions per unit of GDP), and emissions per capita, were chosen for each component to comprehensively represent the respective subsystem. These indicators could underscore the spatial heterogeneity of air pollution control and carbon mitigation performance in the context of local socio-economic status. The index evaluation system of AP-CM system was shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Index evaluation system of AP-CM system

System	Subsystem	Indicators
AP-CM system	Carbon Mitigation	CO ₂ Emission
		CO ₂ Intensity
		CO ₂ Emission per capita
	Air Pollution Control	CO Emission
		CO Intensity
		CO Emission per capita
		SO ₂ Emission
		SO ₂ Intensity
		SO ₂ Emission per capita
		NO _x Emission
		NO _x Intensity
		NO _x Emission per capita
		PM _{2.5} Emission
		PM _{2.5} Intensity
		PM _{2.5} Emission per capita
		PM ₁₀ Emission
		PM ₁₀ Intensity
		PM ₁₀ Emission per capita

3. Methodology

3.1 Ordering degree to evaluate the performance of AP and CM subsystem

To evaluate the performance of each subsystem, ordering degrees were calculated to assess the collaborative development level among indicators within each subsystem (Mu et al., 2022). Therein, the entropy weight method, an objective weights assessment strategy was conducted to allocate weights for each indicator in the AP and CM subsystems, respectively. The calculation process followed the methodology described in the paper by Guo et al. (2023).

3.2 Coupling coordination degree to evaluate the synergy degree in AP-CM system

For assessing the synergy degree of the system, the coupling coordination theory was employed to evaluate the coordination between the Air Pollution (AP) and Carbon Mitigation (CM) subsystems. Recognizing the equal importance of air pollution control and carbon mitigation in China from 2013 to 2020, equal weights ($\alpha=0.5$, $\beta=0.5$) were assigned to each subsystem (Yi et al., 2022). The comprehensive synergy degree of the AP-CM system was then obtained using the weighted averaging method. This step also followed the approach outlined in the study conducted by Guo et al. (2023) to calculate the coupling coordination degree for each province in each year.

3.3 Driving factor analysis on synergy degree

To explore the spatial and temporal characteristics of the influences of potential drivers on the synergistic governance performance between air pollution control and carbon mitigation in China, this study conducts a comparative analysis using three geostatistical models: Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), and Geographically and Temporally Weighted Regression (GTWR). The geostatistical model with consideration of spatial and temporal non-stationarity has the potential possibility to reduce the uncertainty on the explanation of the relationship between the coupling coordination degree and drivers (Comber et al., 2023).

4. Results

4.1 Synergistic governance performance evaluation at national scale

As shown in Figure 1, the red and green dashed line represents the ordering degree of AP and CM subsystem. It is obvious that the national carbon mitigation's ordering degree increases continuously since 2013 (from 0.793 to 0.814 during 2013 - 2018), followed by a slightly drop after 2019 (from 0.726 to 0.724). Whereas the ordering degree of air pollution control present a "U-shape" characteristic from 2016 to 2018, then drop rapidly. Although there are fluctuations from 2013 to 2020, the variation of air pollution control's ordering degree is only 0.003. It makes a comparison with the total variation of carbon mitigation improvement, with a value of 0.057. In terms of coupling coordination degree, the comprehensive synergistic governance performance has not improved dramatically from 2013 to 2020 (from 0.793 to 0.803). The peak value appears in the 2018 with a value of 0.814. Compared among the three time-series lines in Figure 1, it is evident that the relatively uncoordinated air pollution control at the national scale hasn't contributed to the improved performance of synergistic governance between air pollution and carbon mitigation in China.

Figure 1 The ordering degree of AP (in red) and CM (in green) subsystem, as well as the coupling coordination degree of AP-CM system (in blue) at national scale from 2013 to 2020

4.2 Spatial and temporal characteristics of driving factors

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression was conducted for the entire period (2013 - 2020) to identify potential driving factors for subsequent sub-period analysis. The drivers include economic, energy, industrial and population-related variables, which have been listed in the paper by Guo et al. (2023). After screening, the results revealed nine variables with statistical significance, including GDP per capita index (X4), GDP index (X5), value added of the primary industry (X8), value added index of the

secondary industry (X11), raw coal consumption (X16), total energy consumption (X17), electricity consumption (X18), natural gas consumption (X20), and total population (X21). The adjusted R-square indicates a value of 0.813. These nine variables were considered as explanatory factors for each model in the subsequent model fitting comparison. Two model-related parameters, R^2 and AICc, were employed as criteria to evaluate the model fitting degree and accuracy, respectively.

Following the collinearity screening, the selected drivers as explanatory variables were listed in the Table 2 for each period. As for the explanatory ability, the GWR model has the highest fit for periods 2013 – 2017 and 2018 – 2019, indicating a significant difference in the performance among these three models. The GWR model, being non-stationary in space, demonstrates higher accuracy in explaining the spatial characteristics of drivers' influences on synergistic governance performance compared to other models. But it is noticeable that for the year 2020 with the policy implementation of “Blue Sky Defense” and the short-term burst of COVID-19 pandemic, the potential drivers after the screening of the multicollinearity does not present significant spatial heterogeneity of the influence on the synergistic governance performance. The global modelling of OLS can only explain 48.5% variation on the coupling coordination degree for year 2020.

Table 2 Analysis results comparison of OLS, GWR and GWR (2013-2017, 2018-2019, 2020).

Models	OLS	GWR	GTWR
R^2 (2013 - 2017)	0.131	0.972	0.391
AICc (2013 - 2017)	-253.089	-685.26	-299.734
Driving factors (2013 - 2017)	X11 + X16 + X20 + X21		
R^2 (2018-2019)	0.512	0.637	0.508
AICc (2018-2019)	-111.60	-115.477	-110.467
Driving factors (2018 - 2019)	X4 + X5 + X8 + X11 + X16 + X20 + X21		
R^2 (2020)	0.485	0.459	-
AICc (2020)	-42.116	-37.153	-
Driving factors (2020)	X4 + X8 + X16 + X17 + X20		

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reveals that the abatement processes of two policies, namely the “Clean Air Action” and the “Blue Sky Defense”, did not contribute to an improvement in the performance of synergistic governance. The lack of coordination in air pollution control at the national scale has hindered the enhanced performance of synergistic governance between air pollution and carbon mitigation in China. Additionally, the relative activities during the outbreak of COVID-19 have adversely affected the overall performance of synergistic governance on a national scale. From a spatiotemporal perspective, the driving factors exhibit dramatic spatial heterogeneity, although temporal variation remains relatively consistent. This observation suggests a certain level of sustainability in policy implementation for synergy governance. However, the relatively lower explanatory ability for the periods 2018–2019 and 2020 indicates that factors such as energy structure, industrial adjustment, population, and local economic development contribute less to the synergy. To further enhance the study, it is crucial to consider the influence of variables like passenger traffic, the impact of COVID-19 pandemic, and other potential factors. Also, the identified spatial heterogeneity of the influence from drivers highlight "one-fit-one" strategies becomes imperative to align with local circumstances, ensuring the sustainable and resilient application of synergistic governance.

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